

Introducing A Project-Based Learning Model To Develop Students' Critical Thinking

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Annotation: This article discusses the issues of introducing a project-based learning model as an effective pedagogical mechanism for developing critical thinking in students in secondary general education institutions. The study analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations of the concept of critical thinking, substantiates the didactic possibilities of project-based learning, its role in the formation of students' analytical, critical and reflective thinking skills. The article also reveals the stages of project activity, its impact on the development of students' independent research, problem-solving and teamwork competencies.

Keywords: critical thinking, project-based learning, competency-based approach, critical thinking, reflection, educational model, problem-based learning.

Introduction.

In today's globalization and digital transformation, one of the main requirements for the education system is not only to acquire knowledge, but also to form the skills of students to consciously analyze, evaluate and apply it in real life situations. In this regard, the issue of developing critical thinking in the modern educational process is gaining particular relevance. Critical thinking represents the student's ability to justify his or her opinion, draw conclusions based on evidence, view the problem from different perspectives, and analyze his or her activities through reflection.

Traditional teaching approaches often prioritize reproductive thinking and form the student as a subject who receives ready-made knowledge. However, in today's society, the need to educate a person who thinks independently, who can creatively and responsibly approach problem situations is becoming increasingly important. Therefore, the introduction of innovative pedagogical approaches that involve the student in the educational process as an active subject of knowledge and activate his or her thinking processes is of great importance.

Project-based learning is one of such effective pedagogical technologies, which serves to combine students' theoretical knowledge with practical activities. Through this approach, students directly participate in the process of identifying real problems, analyzing them, developing solutions and presenting results. This consistently develops their critical thinking, critical approach, logical conclusion and reflective analysis skills.

At the same time, project activities also have a positive effect on the formation of responsibility, cooperation, self-management and communicative competencies in students. These aspects correspond to the main requirements of the modern

competency-based education paradigm. Thus, the introduction of the project-based learning model into educational practice not only activates students' cognitive activity, but also appears as an important factor ensuring their personal and intellectual development.

Literature review.

In modern pedagogical research, the development of reflective, critical, and critical thinking in students is interpreted as an important factor in improving the quality and effectiveness of education. In particular, in Western pedagogical scientific schools, reflective thinking is studied in close connection with the intellectual maturity of a person, his ability to make independent decisions, and analyze problem situations. The American educator and philosopher John Dewey[1] emphasized the need to form reflective thinking in the educational process through the student's experience-based activities, and scientifically substantiated the fact that teaching organized on the basis of problem situations develops higher levels of thinking.

In subsequent studies, project-based learning has been widely analyzed as an effective pedagogical technology for developing critical thinking. The “project method” developed by William Heard Kilpatrick[2] is explained by the fact that it serves to involve the student in the educational process as an active subject, to develop independent research and a creative approach. Also, David Kolb's[3] experiential learning model opens up the possibilities of deepening knowledge through reflection and drawing thoughtful conclusions in the process of project activities.

The didactic possibilities of project-based learning within the framework of a competency-based approach have also been deeply analyzed in the studies of Uzbek pedagogical scientists. In particular, in the works of N. A. Muslimov[4], B. Kh. Khodjaev[6] and R. H. Jo'rayev[5], it is scientifically substantiated that organizing the educational process on the basis of innovative technologies serves to develop independent thinking, analytical approach and reflective competencies in students. Their research notes that project activities have an effective impact on students' ability to connect knowledge with practice, develop complex problem-solving skills, and develop teamwork skills.

The analyzed literature shows that the project-based learning model creates a favorable pedagogical environment for the development of critical thinking. However, existing studies have not sufficiently addressed the issues of systematically linking this model with students' critical thinking components, as well as improving the mechanisms for implementing it in practice. Therefore, a deeper study of the methodological foundations of developing critical thinking through project-based learning determines the relevance of this article.

Discussion.

The results of the study show that the consistent introduction of the project-based

learning model into the educational process effectively develops the structural components of critical thinking in students - analytical approach, critical assessment, reflection, and logical conclusion skills. While in traditional forms of education, students participate mainly as subjects who receive ready-made knowledge, in project activities they become active participants in the learning process. This situation contributes to students' conscious attitude to the thinking process and deeper assimilation of knowledge.

During the discussion, it was found that the problematic nature of project activities forms the competencies of students to ask questions, make assumptions, and make decisions based on evidence. The presence of the stages of identifying the problem, setting goals, developing solution options, and analyzing results in the projects completed by students allows them to gradually increase their level of critical thinking. In particular, the reflective analysis carried out at the end of the project helps students to look critically at their own activities.

It was also found that the effectiveness of the project-based learning model is directly related to the development of students' social and communicative competencies. During collective project work, students actively participate in the process of justifying their opinions, listening to the points of view of others, and coming to a common conclusion. This strengthens the skills of argumentation and logical reasoning, which are one of the important aspects of critical thinking.

The results of the study are in common with the theoretical views of Western and CIS scientists on project-based learning and reflective thinking. At the same time, the project-based learning model in this study differs from previous works in that it is considered based on a systematic approach as a means of developing critical thinking in students. In particular, the analysis of the substantive, procedural, and outcome components of the model in an interconnected manner increases its practical significance.

However, some limitations were also identified during the discussion. In particular, the methodological training of teachers, the distribution of lesson time, and the clarification of assessment criteria are important factors in the implementation of project-based learning. If project activities are not systematically planned or insufficient attention is paid to the reflection stage, the effectiveness of developing critical thinking may decrease. In general, the results of the discussion allow us to recognize the project-based learning model as an effective pedagogical mechanism for developing critical thinking in students. When introducing this model into educational practice, strengthening methodological support, increasing the professional competencies of teachers, and improving the assessment system are important tasks.

Conclusion

The results of this study confirm that the implementation of the project-based

learning model into the educational process is of significant pedagogical importance in developing critical thinking in students. The theoretical analysis and practical observations have shown that project activities serve to consistently form students' analytical thinking, critical assessment, logical conclusions and reflection skills. Also, reflective analysis carried out in the process of project-based learning serves as an important factor in developing students' skills to critically respond to their own educational activities, to understand mistakes and to improve future activities. This aspect indicates that the development of reflective thinking is continuous and systematic.

In general, the results of the study substantiate that the introduction of the project-based learning model into general secondary education practice is an effective and promising direction for the formation of reflective thinking in students. In order to apply this model in practice, it is recommended to strengthen the methodological training of teachers, improve the criteria for evaluating project activities and pay special attention to the reflection process as important tasks for future research and pedagogical practice.

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